

Automated IC₅₀ shift assay for studying direct and time-dependent inhibition of cytochrome P450 enzymes *in vitro* (1.0.0)

This technical note document contains a description of the setup and specific details of the automated cocktail assay that was published originally in [Kahma et al. 2021](#). In any reference to this methodology, please cite the original publication.

Materials

Equipment

Automated protocols

- Tecan Freedom Evo 150 liquid handling robot (Tecan Group, Männedorf, Switzerland) with a 8-channel liquid handling arm, controlled with Freedom EVOware software.
- Tecan Te-Shake heated orbital shaker (Tecan Group, Männedorf, Switzerland) with a custom-built aluminum 96-well plate block for an incubation plate.
- EcoTherm IC22 chilling dry bath (Torrey Pines Scientific, Carlsbad, CA, USA) with two low-profile 96-well plate blocks (Cat # 620-5041) for reagent and sample plates.
- EcoTherm IC20 chilling dry bath (Torrey Pines Scientific, Carlsbad, CA, USA) with a block for 24 × 1.5 mL Eppendorf tubes (Cat # 620-5043).

Details of the general robot deck layout are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Diagram of the robot deck layout equipped with all the racks, Peltier dry baths and the heating orbital shaker used in the following protocols.

Sample preparation for LC-MS/MS analysis

- Benchtop centrifuge capable of speed of at least 1800 × g when fitted with a deep-well swinging bucket rotor (e.g. Eppendorf 5804 R; Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany).
- GeneVac centrifugal evaporator (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA).

Consumables and Reagents

Automated protocols

- Conductive, disposable liquid-handling (LiHa) tips compatible with the robot (10 µL, 50 µL, 200 µL and 1000 µL) (Tecan Group, Männedorf, Switzerland).
- 1.5 mL amber Eppendorf tubes for reagents (Cat. # 0030120191; Eppendorf, Hamburg, Germany).
- 4-well partitioned reagent reservoirs for reagents (Cat # 390107; Porvair Sciences, Wrexham, UK).
- Non-skirted 96-well PCR plates with a working volume of 200 µL for incubations (e.g. Framestar, Cat. # 4ti-0710; 4-titude, Wotton, UK).
- Non-skirted low-profile 96-well PCR plates with a working volume of 150 µL for reagents and samples (e.g. Framestar, Cat. # 4ti-0720; 4-titude, Wotton, UK).
- Pierceable adhesive films with cross-cut adhesive-free windows for 96-well sample plates (Cat. # 4ti-0566; 4-titude, Wotton, UK).
- Ultrapure water (e.g. Milli-Q)
- Methanol and other solvent(s) of choice, e.g. acetonitrile and/or DMSO.
- 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer, pH 7.4.
- Pooled human liver microsomes (HLMs).
- NADPH or NADPH regenerating system.
- Potential inhibitors/test compounds.
- Selective probe substrates for each CYP investigated.
- Probe reaction metabolites used in calibration standards.
- Internal standards for probe reaction metabolites.

Sample preparation for LC-MS/MS analysis

- Impact protein precipitation 2 mL square well filter plates (Cat # CE0-7565; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA).
- 2 mL conical 96-well collection plates (Cat # AH0-7194; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA).
- 96-square silicone plate seals (Cat # AH0-8597; Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA).

Protocol

The protocol consists of automated preparatory scripts, automated incubation script and manual sample preparation for LC-MS/MS analysis. An overview of the automated preparatory procedure is depicted in Figure 2. We recommend using thoroughly tested and well-validated liquid classes for each solvent and matrix used in the robot scripts.

Figure 2. Overview of the automated preparatory steps before IC_{50} shift experiment.

Substrate and metabolite dilutions (automated)

Each probe substrate can be diluted separately or in a cocktail of several probe substrates. We have validated two different substrate cocktails including substrates for CYP1A2, CYP2B6, CYP2C8, CYP2C9 and CYP3A4 (Cocktail I), and CYP2A6, CYP2C19, CYP2D6 and CYP2J2 (Cocktail II) (Kahma *et al.* 2021). The substrate cocktails are made in 80% methanol. The amount of substrates should be adjusted to a 200 times higher concentration than that in the final incubation. The concentrations of the metabolite dilutions are calculated based on the concentrations needed in the calibration standards. The robot prepares a maximum of 400 μL of each solution.

- 1) Prepare stock solutions of probe substrates and the metabolites used in LC-MS/MS quantitation.
- 2) Prepare the robotic workstation and select an appropriate script.

- 3) Check that the deck layout and all the labware matches the layout shown on the script window (Figure 3).
- 4) Fill the labware with the appropriate solutions (solvents and stock solutions).
- 5) Run the script.
- 6) Divide the prepared solutions into several aliquots based on the consumption of the solutions.
- 7) Store the dilutions at -20 °C if not used on the same day.

Figure 3. Diagram of the robot deck layout equipped with the racks and labware used in the scripts for substrate and metabolite dilutions. Please, see Figure 1 for further details.

Calibration standard and quality control preparation (automated)

A set of calibration standards and quality controls can be freshly prepared on the day of the actual experiment. In case of solubility issues, methanol or other solvent can be added in the standards.

- 1) Prepare a matrix solution containing heat-inactivated human liver microsomes in 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer. Use the same microsomal protein concentration as used in the incubations.
- 2) Prepare the robotic workstation and select an appropriate script.
- 3) Check that the deck layout and all the labware matches the layout shown on the script window (Figure 4).
- 4) Fill the labware with the appropriate solutions (matrix and metabolite solutions).

5) Run the script.

6) Store the standards at 4 °C before placing them in the Eppendorf rack at the end of the timed IC₅₀ shift script.

Figure 4. Diagram of the robot deck layout equipped with the racks and labware used in the scripts for preparation of calibration standards and quality controls. Please, see Figure 1 for further details.

Incubation and sample plate preparation (automated)

The plate preparation script should be run right before the timed incubation script. At the beginning of the plate preparation script, the temperature of the heating orbital shaker is set to 39.2 °C in order to warm the shaker before the beginning of the actual incubation script.

- 1) Prepare HLM and NADPH working solutions in sodium phosphate buffer and an internal standard solution in methanol. HLM and NADPH solutions can be stored on ice before they are needed in the script.
- 2) Turn on the Peltier chilling dry bath and set the temperature to 4 °C.
- 3) Prepare the robotic workstation and select an appropriate script.
- 4) Check that the deck layout and all the labware matches the layout shown on the script window (Figure 5).
- 5) Fill the labware with the appropriate solutions (sodium phosphate buffer, internal standard solution, solvent for controls, substrate and inhibitor solutions, HLMs and NADPH).
- 6) Run the script (for plate layouts and script steps, see Figure 2).

7) Place a pierceable film on the sample plate and attach the plate firmly on the chilling dry bath. NOTE: Pipetting may lift the plate from the dry bath block if the plate is not attached to the block.

Figure 5. Diagram of the robot deck layout equipped with the racks and labware used in the incubation and sample plate preparation script. Please, see Figure 1 for further details.

IC₅₀ shift assay (automated)

Based on temperature measurements in the incubation wells, the heating orbital shaker is set to 39.2 °C to produce a temperature of 37 °C in the incubation matrix. The shaking speed is set at 550 rpm. NOTE: To thoroughly mix the HLMs and the incubation mixture during the timed script, mixing with the tips by aspirating and dispensing is also needed before and after the addition of reagents and sampling.

- 1) Fill the tip racks (full tip racks needed because of timing) and select an appropriate script.
- 2) Check that the deck layout and all the labware matches the layout shown on the script window (Figure 6).
- 3) Place the prepared incubation plate on the heated shaker.
- 4) Run the script (for plate layouts, see Figure 2).

Script steps for time-dependent inhibition (TDI):

- Addition of HLMs (10 µL) and NADPH (10 µL) to columns 1-3
→ 30-minute preincubation.

- Addition of substrates (1 μL) to columns 1-3
→ 5-minute incubation (final incubation volume 200 μL).
- 30 μL sample into 90 μL of internal standard solution (columns 1-3 of the sample plate).

Script steps for slow binding inhibition:

- Addition of HLMs (10 μL) to columns 4-6
→ 30-minute preincubation.
- Addition of substrates (1 μL) and NADPH (10 μL) to columns 4-6.
→ 5-minute incubation (final incubation volume 200 μL).
- 30 μL sample into 90 μL of internal standard solution (columns 4-6 of the sample plate).

Script steps for direct inhibition (DI):

- Addition of HLMs (10 μL) to columns 7-9
→ 3-minute warm-up
- Addition of NADPH (10 μL) to columns 7-9
→ 5-minute incubation (final incubation volume 200 μL).
- 30 μL sample into 90 μL of internal standard solution (columns 7-9 of the sample plate).

Figure 6. Diagram of the robot deck layout equipped with the racks and labware used in the timed incubation script. Please, see Figure 1 for further details.

5) At the end of the timed script, place the calibration standards and QCs to the Eppendorf rack. The robot then takes a 30 μL sample of each standard and QC to the sample plate (columns 10-11).

6) To precipitate the proteins in the samples, keep the sample plate on the chilling dry bath (4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) for 30 minutes before sample preparation.

Sample preparation (manual)

- 1) Move the samples from the 96-well plate to a filter plate (Impact protein precipitation plate).
- 2) Place a 2 mL conical 96-well collection plate underneath the filter plate.
- 3) Centrifuge (1800 g, 15 min, 8 °C) the samples through the filter.
- 4) Evaporate the samples to dryness using vacuum (GeneVac centrifugal evaporator) at 58 °C.
- 5) Reconstitute the samples with a solvent of choice (for the substrate cocktails, we use 30-40 µL of 20% methanol).
- 6) Seal the plate with a pierceable silicone plate seal.
- 7) Centrifuge the samples (2000 g, 15 min, 8 °C).

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